

An Extensive Study of Methods and Techniques for Teaching Writing Skills to Intermediate Level Students

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Abstract

This research paper is concerned with teaching writing skills to students at intermediate level. Writing is a productive process. So it is an instrument for both communication and self-expression. Writing is one of the most important things for university students. Good writing skills are essential for their success as they have to write essays, letters and prepare research papers, or to take tests. In this paper, the 46-item questionnaires concerning with teaching writing skills were given to teachers of English specialization from Yadanabon University, Mandalay. The 46-item questionnaire was prepared to investigate how teachers of English specialization teach writing skill to the intermediate level students. This paper also presents how the researcher tried to promote essay writing of 30 students from third year, Cooperative College by giving a model essay and doing three tests. They were asked to write an essay without being taught. Then the weaknesses were remedied. Secondly, the students were given a model essay and they were asked to write another essay similar to the model one. Then the weaknesses were remedied. Thirdly, the students were asked to write another essay. In this paper, pre-writing techniques are presented. The purpose of this research paper is to encourage self-expression, to foster self-esteem, enhance communication skill, and improve the students' interest and confidence in their writing.

Key words: methods, techniques, writing, skill, tests

Introduction

Traditionally, learning a foreign language is learning the four language skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing. Today, in our country Myanmar, English plays a vital role in the education system as English has been taught from the primary school level to the intermediate level, i.e, University level. At the primary school level and middle school level, English is a subject in itself in the school curriculum but in the high school level, English is not only a school curriculum in itself but also a medium of instruction for science subjects. At the intermediate level, English is the medium of instruction in teaching of all specializations except Myanmar. Actually, the aim of English language teaching in Myanmar is to develop the four language skills but the emphasis is placed on the development of reading and writing skills rather than listening and speaking as written examination system is conducted. Good writing skills are essential for intermediate level students to write reports on readings or lab work, prepare research papers, or take essay tests but most of intermediate level students are very weak in writing. Actually, writing is one of the most important things for University students. Writing is an instrument for both communication and self-expression. Furthermore, writing is the commonest way of examining students' performance in English. The purpose of this research paper is to improve the writing skill of intermediate level students. So, some questions concerning with teaching writing skills were asked to 10 teachers of English specialization from Yadanabon University, Mandalay. Moreover, some prewriting techniques are discussed in this paper. This paper also presents the progress of intermediate level students' essay writing abilities by giving a model essay and doing three tests. This research paper entitled "An Extensive Study of Methods and Techniques for Teaching Writing Skills to Intermediate Level Students" will be of great help to teachers of English specialization to give the idea of what methods and techniques should be used for promoting the writing skills of the intermediate level students.

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Language skills

A person who uses English well has a number of different abilities. He may read books, write letters and speak to others or listen to the radio/CD tapes. Thus, we can identify four major skills: listening and understanding, speaking, reading and understanding and writing. Listening and reading are receptive skills in that the language user is receiving written or spoken language. On the other hand, speaking and writing skills involve some kind of production on the part of the language user, and so they are known as productive skills. So, the four major language skills can be summarized as follows:

SKILL \ MEDIUM	SPEECH	WRITTEN WORD
RECEPTIVE	Listening and understanding	Reading and understanding
PRODUCTIVE	Speaking	Writing

However, this summary is general and we might well isolate a number of more detailed *sub-skills*. For example, the writing of an academic paper is very different from the writing of an informal letter. These will be very different from the writing of a postcard style writing or writing dialogue, etc.

The importance and nature of writing

Today more and more people need to learn to write in English for occupational or academic purposes. Actually, writing is based on thinking. One thinks before writing, while writing and afterwards, while reading what has been written. If a person has no writing practice, he will have no thinking practice. A person who lacks reading and thinking will have no idea to write although the topic for writing is very easy. Thinking skill can be promoted by writing more and more with own ideas. A person who practises expressing his own thoughts and ideas will become a good writer who can express his own thoughts and ideas easily and clearly. In this way, a good thinker will become a good writer.

The role of English in Myanmar

In our country, Myanmar, English has been taught as a foreign language and as a school curriculum since the primary school level. Moreover, in the high school level, all the science subjects are taught through English. Nowadays, in all fields of universities and colleges except Myanmar subject, English is used as a medium of instruction. So, the students who are learning at universities and colleges should develop the four language skills. Nowadays, our country is practicing open market-oriented economic system. So, English is essential for us to have an excellent command of English as we have to deal with foreigners. Moreover, under the guidance of ministry of education, English is being applied in every field of our country. So, English is the key to scientific and technical knowledge essential to the development of our country.

The needs and weaknesses of Myanmar students

In our country, Myanmar, although intermediate level students concern themselves with writing skills, most of them always face with difficulty in writing. This is because they do not have enough vocabulary and don't know clearly how to use the tenses correctly. Moreover, they cannot construct even correct simple sentences clearly as well as do not practise expressing their own thoughts and ideas. They are also very reluctant to write or write too little. So they are very weak in writing skill.

Pre-writing Techniques

Unlike speaking, writing is always learned in school and it takes time to master. Writing is a complex skill, made up of dozens of previously acquired sub-skills from handwriting and spelling to syntax and organization. It is a personal creative expression with roots in our spontaneous needs for communicating with others and ourselves. To create a piece of writing, one must get an idea about something to say in his paper. To get one's idea down on paper quickly and to make one's job of writing easier, some pre-writing techniques are discussed.

Pre-writing

Pre-writing is much easier to begin drafting a paper when we already have many ideas about what we want to say. It is the preparation and explanation that writers engage in before they actually begin to draft. These techniques are designed to get ideas down on paper quickly; generally the quantity of ideas and words is more important than their quality. They provide opportunities for students to explore their thoughts to get started, to break through the blank page, to prompt thinking, to jar the memory, and to discover ideas and subjects, which are hidden beneath the surface.

Listing

In the book 'The Act of Writing', Gould (1989) presents listing as

"Listing frees writers from the structure of sentences, paragraphs, and the spelling of words, enabling them to keep pace with their thoughts. By recording thoughts in lists often through the use of abbreviation, scribbling, and drawings, you can create a skeletal framework of your thinking. You can work listing particularly in innovative patterns such as circles, diagonals, clusters or tree diagrams, which encourage fresh perspectives on your topics."

Brainstorming

Brainstorming is a problem-solving strategy commonly used by groups of people. It works particularly well when we really do not know what to do or think, or when we cannot make a decision. It is a powerful public strategy for generating information and ideas because it taps a group's potential and brings numerous receptive atmospheres, an environment that accepts all ideas as possible solutions for the problems or steps towards the goal.

In the book, 'Writing Reading Research', Viet and Clifford(1985) state brainstorming as

"Brainstorming is used by writers, business people, and scientists to help them unblock their thinking. It is a way of bringing to mind as many ideas about a topic as you can. Brainstorming not only provides you with raw materials to work with, but it also gets your creative juices flowing. You can brainstorm out loud or on paper. One way is to write down all the words or phrases about a topic that pop into your head, listing them down the page, one after the other as they occur to you. Don't judge them or worry about being consistent. Sometimes you have to go through three or four or even a dozen useless ideas before a good one comes along. The purpose of this technique is to let the associations connect with one another in the mind, like rubbing stick together to create a spark."

Free writing

Free writing is a form of free association similar to brainstorming but it is a private, personal information gathering strategy. In the book 'Writing Reading Research', Viet and Clifford, (1985) advise as

"Begin writing about your topic at a steady, normal pace, jotting down whatever comes to mind, and continue without stopping for a planned amount of time, perhaps five or ten minutes. Do not try to screen or organize your ideas; simply let them flow. Don't worry about spelling or

repetition or punctuation or even making sense. You don't do free writing for others to read; **rather you do it** for yourself to think through your topic and come up with ideas that you can use later."

Journal writing

The journal is also a place where students record a variety of writing activities (note books, daybooks, commonplace books, or diaries). Using journal writing gives students a particular place to accumulate writing-to-learn activities. The activities for the journal can vary in degrees of informality and in the tightness of their forms. Journal writing can be used to structure the class and to give students opportunities to interact with class material.

Journal writing can also be used to begin class e.g. by giving a prompt idea that is related to previous day's discussion. After allowing five minutes for responding freely to this prompt, a student might be asked to read his/ her response to initiate discussion. These writing activities work well to bridge students' other activities, such as a previous class, and to set the mood for English class. Journal writing is also useful as a means to focus student's attention during the class. For example, the teacher could interrupt the discussion and ask students to write for five minutes about a particular controversial notion. Writing down thoughts often helps students to sort out the difficult portions and to make sense of concepts that are confusing and complex. It can also be used to end the class by posing a summarizing question, such as "what one thing did you learn today?" The students are asked this kind of question to synthesize the material for themselves. Journal writing can be done not only in the class but also outside the classroom by giving as assignments.

Clustering

Clustering is the act of associating our pre-writing response around a nucleus or dominant idea. This is also referred to as mapping or tree diagrams.

In the book 'The Macmillan Guide for Teachers of Writing', Smith (1991) discusses clustering as

"A cluster is a visual and verbal representation of a student's potential piece of writing. As a prewriting technique, the cluster has a number of advantages over the previously mentioned prewriting techniques because the student creates ideas, generates words and phrases, and organizes theses into relationship with grades from lowest to highest as he clusters. For this reason, if students have time for only one pre-writing activity for time limited essay, clustering is a winner. If they have time for more than one prewriting, clustering is an excellent follow up to brainstorming."

By means of clustering, the teacher can demonstrate visually what clear organization looks like, facilitating well-organized final essays. Since clustering can visually display the hierarchy of ideas, it is also an excellent way to show students where they need more details and examples on a more specific level of paragraph. So if students have a good cluster map, they can fold their bubbles and branches up into good paragraphs.

Thus, it is hoped that all pre-writing techniques discussed above will be of great aids to teachers of English specialization for teaching writing skills to students.

Collecting Data from English Teachers of Yadanabon University, Mandalay

This research paper is "An Extensive Study of Methods and Techniques for Teaching Writing Skills to Students at Intermediate Level". So, it is necessary to know what methods and techniques are mostly used by teachers of English specialization for teaching writing skills to students at intermediate level, whether these methods are suitable to the students; and how they teach to improve their students' writing skill at intermediate level.

For this research paper, a 46-item questionnaire was given to each of the ten teachers of English Specialization, who all answered the questions. There are 46-items in my questionnaire, 15 items of which are based on Jane Willis's 'Teaching English through English' (1983) and the remaining items are the techniques for teaching writing skills at intermediate level.

Questionnaire

I beg you to answer the following Questionnaire.

To promote the Writing skills of your students (Intermediate level)

Writing

1	Do you give your students model writing before they write down their essay?	Yes	No
2	Do you give your students the outlines concerning your essay topic before they are asked to write?	Yes	No
3	Do you teach your students the use of tenses before the essay writing?	Yes	No
4	Do you teach your students the use of tenses after the essay writing?	Yes	No
5	Do you discuss the sentence structures before writing?	Yes	No
6	Do you discuss the sentence structures after their writing?	Yes	No
7	Do you teach them the use of conjunctions before essay writing?	Yes	No
8	Do you teach them how to use conjunctions after essay writing?	Yes	No
9	Do you teach them the use of prepositions before essay writing?	Yes	No
10	Do you teach them the use of prepositions after essay writing?	Yes	No
11	Do you teach them the use of articles before essay writing?	Yes	No
12	Do you teach them how to use articles after essay writing?	Yes	No
13	Do you make them write individually?	Yes	No
14	Do you make them write as group work?	Yes	No
15	Do you give them a limited time?	Yes	No
16	Do you limit how many words they have to write?	Yes	No
17	Do you say to write in three paragraphs?	Yes	No
18	Do you say to write more than three paragraphs?	Yes	No
19	Do you make them write the essays in class only?	Yes	No
20	Do you make them write the essays as homework only?	Yes	No
21	Do you make them write the essays not only in class but also at home?	Yes	No
22	Do you make them write only for preparing for their examination?	Yes	No
23	Do you make them write for improving their writing quality?	Yes	No
24	Do you teach them essay writing once a week?	Yes	No
25	Do you teach them essay writing twice a month?	Yes	No
26	Do you train them for writing letters?	Yes	No
27	Do you train them for note writing?	Yes	No
28	Do you train them for writing summary?	Yes	No
29	Do you teach them paraphrasing?	Yes	No
30	Do you teach them prewriting?	Yes	No
31	Do you teach them listing?	Yes	No
32	Do you teach them brainstorming?	Yes	No
33	Do you teach them free writing?	Yes	No
34	Do you teach them journal writing?	Yes	No
35	Do you teach them clustering?	Yes	No
36	Do you teach them descriptive writing?	Yes	No
37	Do you teach them expository writing?	Yes	No
38	Do you teach them narrative writing?	Yes	No
39	Do you teach them argumentative writing?	Yes	No
40	Do you teach them business writing?	Yes	No
41	Do you teach them writing with cohesion?	Yes	No
42	Do you teach them outlining?	Yes	No
43	Do you teach them expanding from key ideas?	Yes	No

44	Do you teach them postcard style writing?	Yes	No
45	Do you teach them altering dictations?	Yes	No
46	Do you teach them paragraphing?	Yes	No

The above questionnaire was given to teachers of English specialization. They did not need to mention their names. The questionnaires were collected the next day so that they had enough time to think and answer the questions. Thus, it can be assumed that the answers given by them are more reliable.

An Overall View

It has been observed that 90% of teachers gave their students model writing while 100% of teachers gave their students outlines concerning the essay topic before they were asked to write. Again, 70% of teachers taught their students the use of tenses before the essay writing but 20% of teachers taught their students the use of tenses after the essay writing. Next, 70% of teachers discussed sentence structures before writing and 70% of teachers discussed sentence structures after writing. Moreover, 50% of teachers taught their students the use of conjunctions before the essay writing and 50% of teachers taught their students the use of conjunctions after the essay writing. Furthermore, 40% of teachers taught their students the use of prepositions before the essay writing and 40% of teachers taught their students the use of prepositions after the essay writing. Again, 50% of teachers taught the use of articles before the essay writing and 50% of teachers taught the use of articles after the essay writing. Next, 90% of teachers made their students write individually whereas 40% of teachers made their students write as group work. Moreover, 50% of teachers gave their students a limited time but 30% of teachers limited the number of words students have to write. Again, 100% of teachers said to write in three paragraphs but 10% of teachers said to write more than three paragraphs. Next, 10% of teachers made their students write the essays in class only whereas 10% of teachers made their students write the essays as homework. Moreover, 90% of teachers made their students write the essays not only in class but also at home while 20% of teachers made their students write only for preparing for their examination. Again, 80% of teachers made their students write for improving their writing quality. Next, 60% of teachers taught their students essay writing once a week while 30% of teachers taught their students essay writing twice a month. As an overall view, by studying the teachers' answers, it has been observed that most of the teachers have trained their students well for writing essays. Actually, teaching writing essays is an extensive writing. So by training students in writing essays, their writing ability will improve more. In this way, they will become skillful in writing skill. Moreover, it has been observed that 100% of teachers trained their students for writing letters. Again, 70% of teachers trained their students for note writing and 70% of teachers trained their students for writing summary. Moreover, 80% of teachers taught the students paraphrasing and 90% of teachers taught their students prewriting. Furthermore, 50% of teachers taught their students listing and 60% of teachers taught their students brainstorming. Again, 60% of teachers taught their students free writing and 50% of teachers taught their students clustering. Next, 10% of teachers gave practice journal writing.

Furthermore, 100% of teachers taught their students about descriptive writing, expository writing, narrative writing and argumentative writing while 30% of teachers taught their students business writing. Moreover, 80% of teachers taught the students about writing with cohesion but there was no teacher who taught the students outlining. Again 20% of teachers taught the students expanding from key ideas whereas 100% of teachers did not teach their students postcard style writing and altering dictations. Next, only 20% of teachers teach their students paragraphing.

From my point of view as a teacher of English specialization, English teachers should teach all these writing techniques and methods to their students because the students can express their own thoughts and ideas clearly by being taught all these writing techniques and methods. They will also have self-confidence and self-esteem in their ability of writing. In this way, it is hoped that the students' writing skill will become higher.

Teaching Writing Essay

In our country, Myanmar, although students are attending at the university, i.e. intermediate level, most of the students cannot express their own ideas clearly what they want to say. This is because they are very weak in writing. They don't have enough vocabulary and don't know how to use the tenses appropriately. The biggest problem with writing is that students are reluctant to write and write too little. Moreover, writing focuses on form rather than the communication of meaning and there is very little social interaction. So, the purpose of teaching writing essays to the intermediate level students is to know how to use the tenses correctly, to promote students' writing quality and to encourage self-expression. Besides developing creativity, these exercises can reduce the affective filter, foster self-esteem, enhance communication skill, and improve the students' interest and confidence in learning to read and write in English.

Teaching descriptive writing

Firstly, the students were given a model essay about 'My Best Friend' as follows and made them copy this essay and asked to underline all the verbs there and said to look carefully which tenses are mostly used.

My Best Friend

Being a student, I have many friends. Among them, Mya Mya is my best friend. She is a beautiful girl of medium height and build. She has straight and long black hair. She has round face and a fair complexion. Her most outstanding feature is her eyes. They are wide, dark-brown and very innocent as a child. When she smiles she shows a set of fine teeth.

There is a perfect understanding between us and we have similar tastes. Both of us like walking early in the morning and playing table tennis. Both of us have the same hobbies such as reading and gardening. Neither of us cares for frivolities such as watching stage-shows, sitting and chatting in a teashop. She is not only beautiful and charming but also clever in the class. She is always at the top of the class.

I admire her good qualities. She is always kind, helpful and polite to everybody. Although she is intelligent and gifted, she is never boastful. She helps me in my lessons and she always stands by me whenever I encounter with difficulties. She always guides me to walk in the right path to reach our goal. In fact, she is an 'all-weather friend' not a 'fair-weather friend'. For these reasons, she became friends with me and became my best friend.

By studying the model essay about describing a person, it may be seen that the present simple is mostly used except the last sentence which is written using past simple. After the above model essay was given, I explained the tenses patterns and the sentence structures used in the model essay.

Writing essays based on the model one

After explaining the model essay, the students were asked to write a similar essay about "Myself" without giving outline. In 1st Essay Writing Test, "Myself", it was found that most of the students were very weak in writing. The common mistakes and the use of conjunction, article, preposition, as well as tenses were explained. Then an essay on "My Teacher", 2nd Essay Writing Test, was to be written in the class. This was similar in type to the model one and 1st Essay Writing Test. The students were given some outlines to expand and encouraged to add some more points.

Some outlines were given as follows:

"My Teacher"

- being a student – have a lot of teachers
- my favourite one – age
- tall or short – fat or thin
- kind – understanding eyes
- dresses neatly – never late for school
- good at teaching – although good-natured-strict
- a model teacher

Before their own essays were written, they were guided how to expand these outlines and discussed some relevant structures. They were permitted to discuss each other while they were writing. After the essays were checked, their common mistakes were explained and their scores were recorded.

Writing an essay based on the model one

Next students were asked to write another essay, which was similar in type to the model essay and 1st Test and 2nd Test. They were given some outlines to expand and they were encouraged to add some more points.

The students were given some outlines as follows:

"Why I Love My Parents"

- the foundation of a happy family life-love
- treat one another kindly and tenderly – lead a happy and peaceful life
- parents' names – jobs
- ages – hobbies
- treat family very kindly
- help in school lessons
- encourage to try very hard to succeed in life
- scold or beat
- provide with everything-need.

Before their own essays were written, they were discussed how to expand these outlines and explained some relevant structures. Group discussion was conducted in the class before they wrote. After their essays were checked, their mistakes were explained and their scores were recorded.

Table 1 For 1st Essay Writing Test

No. of Students	Spelling	Tenses Usage	Idea Expression	Conjunction	Article Usage	Preposition	Frequency Adverb	Paragraph No.	Sentence No.	Scores
1	2	1	1	-	1	3	-	3	22	4
2	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	1	8	2
3	-	1	1	-	1	-	1	3	18	4
4	-	2	2	-	1	2	-	3	25	4
5	-	3	1	-	1	-	-	3	19	3
6	-	-	4	-	-	-	1	2	17	3
7	2	1	-	-	-	1	-	3	21	4
8	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	3	19	4
9	2	1	1	1	1	-	-	3	16	3
10	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	1	9	2
11	1	2	3	-	1	-	-	3	16	3
12	-	3	1	-	3	1	1	3	19	3
13	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	1	9	2
14	2	-	3	-	1	1	1	3	26	4
15	-	2	2	1	2	1	-	3	20	3
16	1	1	2	1	1	-	-	3	15	3
17	-	2	2	1	2	1	-	3	17	3
18	2	2	3	1	1	2	-	3	19	3
19	1	1	2	-	2	1	-	3	17	3
20	2	2	2	-	1	2	-	3	22	3

Table 2 for 2nd Essay Writing Test

No. of Students	Spelling	Tenses Usage	Idea Expression	Conjunction	Article Usage	Preposition	Frequency Adverb	Paragraph No.	Sentence No.	Scores
1	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	3	22	5
2	2	-	1	-	-	-	-	3	19	4
3	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	3	22	5
4	-	2	-	1	-	-	-	3	26	5
5	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	3	24	5
6	1	1	2	-	-	2	-	3	25	4
7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	25	6
8	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	3	26	6
9	-	3	2	1	-	-	-	3	23	4
10	-	2	-	-	1	1	-	3	15	3
11	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	3	19	4
12	2	-	1	-	-	-	-	3	22	4
13	-	2	-	1	1	-	-	3	17	3
14	2	-	-	1	-	-	1	3	25	5
15	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	3	18	4
16	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	3	20	4
17	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	3	17	4
18	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	3	18	4
19	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	3	22	5
20	1	1	1	-	1	-	-	3	20	4

Table 3 for 3rd Essay Writing Test

No. of Students	Spelling	Tenses Usage	Idea Expression	Conjunction	Article Usage	Preposition	Frequency Adverb	Paragraph No.	Sentence No.	Scores
1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	3	28	6
2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	21	5
3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	25	6
4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	27	7
5	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	3	27	6
6	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	3	29	6
7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	31	8
8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	30	8
9	3	2	-	-	-	-	-	3	33	6
10	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	3	25	5
11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	23	5
12	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	3	24	5
13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	24	5
14	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	3	31	7
15	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	23	5
16	2	-	1	-	-	-	-	3	27	5
17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	23	5
18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	21	5
19	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	3	27	6
20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	23	5

Data Collection and Data Analysis Procedures

As this paper is concerned with teaching writing skills, some questions concerning Teaching Writing skills to students at intermediate level were given to the teachers of English specialization from Yadanabon University, Mandalay. Then, a survey on the thirty students of Third Year about writing essay was conducted.

First, the students were given a model essay about 'My Best Friend'. Next, the sentence structures and the tenses used in this essay were explained. Then, they were asked to write a similar essay about 'Myself' without giving outlines.

Marks allowed to the essay was (10) marks. Their grading scores can be classified as follows:

Marks	Grade
9-10	Super high grade IV
6-8	High grade III
4-5	Average grade II
0-3	Poor grade

Qualitative evaluation on 1st test

Table 4. The grade of the students' scores in the first composition test

Grade	Percentage of students
Grade IV	-
Grade III	-
Grade II	30%
Grade I	70%

According to Table 4 for 1st Essay Writing Test, it may be known that 70% of students got Grade I and 30% of students got Grade II. There was no student who got Grade III and Grade IV.

Figure 1. The graph of the students' writing quality percentage for 1st test

According to Figure 1, in essay writing about 'Myself', it was seen that 50% of the students could write without spelling mistakes but 50% of the students made spelling mistakes. This is because although they are intermediate level students, most of the students are very poor in vocabulary.

Examples:

Instead of	They write
<i>Intelligent</i>	<i>Intelligence</i>
<i>Peaceful</i>	<i>Peacefull</i>
<i>Future time</i>	<i>Feature time</i>

Concerning the use of tenses, only 20% of the students could write in correct tenses, 80% of the students could not write correctly. They were explained about the tenses used in the model essay. This essay, 'Myself', was a similar essay to the model one. So, they have known that they must mostly use present simple in this essay. Here, in writing about 'Myself', they used present simple but they couldn't construct the sentences correctly. This was because most of the students could not write accordingly to 'Subject-Verb Agreement' and some of the students did not know the present continuous form. Most of the students made mistakes as follows:

- (1) I wants a peaceful life.
- (2) I go to school at 8 o'clock and came back at 3 o'clock.
- (3) I hardworking in my lessons.
- (4) All my friends are love me as their sister.
- (5) It give me pleasure.

In dealing with idea expression, 15% of the students could write clearly what they want to express but 85% did not write. This is because although they are intermediate level students, they are very weak in writing skill.

Some of the students were incorrect in expressing their ideas as follows:

Examples:

- (1) I am to be a kindly girl of among my friends.
- (2) I'd like cold-like.
- (3) My parents can serve to pleasure and peaceful out life.

In the use of conjunctions, 70% of the students could use conjunctions correctly whereas 30% of the students could not. In the use of article, 20% of the students could use the articles correctly but 80% of the students could not. In concerning with the use of prepositions, 50% of the students could write correctly but 50% did not write. In dealing with the use of frequency adverbs, the percentage of students who could use frequency adverbs correctly was 80%. So, 20% of the students did not use frequency adverbs correctly.

In the 1st Essay Writing Test, about "Myself", it was found that most of the students were very weak in writing, they were very poor in vocabulary and they couldn't construct the sentences correctly. So, although the topic, 'Myself', was very easy, they could not write clearly what they wanted to express. Some students could not use present simple appropriately according to Subject – Verb Agreement.

So, after checking their 1st Essay Writing Test, present simple, present continuous, the use of conjunctions, articles, prepositions and frequency adverbs were explained.

Qualitative evaluation on 2nd test

Then, they were asked to write an essay on 'my Teacher', 2nd Essay Writing Test, in the class. This was similar in type with the model one, and 1st Essay Writing Test. The students were given some outlines to expand and encouraged to add some more points. Before they wrote down their own, they were guided how to expand these outlines and discussed some relevant structures. They were permitted to discuss each other while they were writing.

Table 5. The grade of the students' scores in 2nd Essay Writing Test

Grade	Percentage of students
Grade IV	-
Grade III	10%
Grade II	80%
Grade I	10%

According to table 52 for 2nd Essay Writing Test, it can be known that 10% of students got Grade I, 80% of students got Grade II and 10% of students got Grade III. But there was no student who got Grade IV.

In this 2nd Essay Writing Test, most of the students could get higher marks than the 1st Test. So they got higher grade than 1st Essay Writing Test.

Figure 2. The graph of the students' writing quality percentage for 2nd Test

According to Figure 2, in 2nd Essay Writing Test about "My Teacher", 65% of the students could write without spelling mistakes but 35% of the students made spelling mistakes.

In dealing with the use of tenses, 50% of the students could write the correct tense forms whereas 50% of the students could not write appropriate tense forms. Some students made mistakes as follows:

- Examples:
- (1) We never boring while she is teaching.
 - (2) He always go to school early and regularly.
 - (3) Although she has good-natured, she has strict.

In concerning with idea expression, 60% of the student could write clearly what they want to say, however, 40% of the students could not write. In the use of conjunctions, 80% of the students could use conjunctions appropriately but 20% of the students could not use appropriately. In the use of articles, 65% of the students could use correctly whereas 35% of the students could not use correctly. In the use of prepositions 85% of the students could write correctly but 15% could not write. In dealing with frequency adverbs, 90% of students could use frequency adverb correctly. So the percentage of students who could not use frequency adverb correctly is 10%.

In this 2nd Essay Writing Test, it was noticed that the students' writing quality is better than the 1st Test. They could write better than the 1st Essay Writing Test. So, their writing quality percentage in each role is higher than the first one. However, the students' common mistakes were explained.

Qualitative evaluation on 3rd test

Students were asked to write a similar essay, "Why I Love My Parents", 3rd Essay Writing Test. This was similar in type with the model one and 1st Test and 2nd Test. They were given some outlines to expand and they were encouraged to add some more points. Before they wrote down their own, they were asked to discuss how to expand these outlines and some relevant structures were explained. They were asked to write in the class and permitted to discuss with each other before they were writing.

Table 6. The grade of the students' scores in 3rd Essay Writing Test

Marks	Percentage students
Grade IV	-
Grade III	50%
Grade II	50%
Grade I	-

According to table 6 for 3rd Essay writing Test, it can be seen that there was no student who got Grade I. And 50% of students got Grade II and Grade III. But there was no student who got Grade IV. In this 3rd Essay Writing Test, most of the students could get higher marks than the 2nd Test. And so they got higher grade than the 2nd Essay Writing Test.

The students' grammatical writing quality percentage can be expressed by graph as in Figure 3.

As it is stated in Figure 3, in 3rd Essay Writing Test about "Why I Love My parents", 80% of the students could write without spelling mistakes whereas 20% of the students made spelling mistakes.

In the use of tenses, 85% of the students could use the tenses correctly but 15% of the students could not use appropriately. Some students made mistake as follows:

- (1) He is treats his family very kindly.
- (2) She always clean her house.

- (3) He is reading the knowledgeable books in his leisure time.
- (4) My mother's hobbies is cooking.
- (5) My parents are encourage me to try very hard to succeed in life.

Figure 3. The graph of the students' writing quality percentage for 3rd Test

In concerning with idea expression, 85% of the students could write clearly what they want to express but 15% of the students could not write correctly as what they wanted to say. In the use of conjunctions, 90% of the students could use conjunctions correctly whereas 10% of the students could not use appropriately. In dealing with the use of articles, 95% of the students could use the articles correctly but 5% of the students could not use. In the use of prepositions, all students could use prepositions correctly. So, the percentage of students who could use prepositions correctly is 100%. In the use of frequency adverbs, 100% of the students could use frequency adverbs correctly.

In this 3rd Essay Writing Test, it was found that the students could write better than the 2nd Test. So the students' writing quality is higher than the 2nd Test. The 2nd Test's quality is higher than the 1st Test's. Thus, the 3rd Test's quality is the highest one among the three tests.

Comparing Qualitative Data from the Results of Three Tests

The students' writing quality percentage in each role from the results of three tests are compared and expressed by graph as follows:

Figure 4. The graph of the students' writing quality percentage from the results of three tests

According to Figure 4, it can be seen that in the 1st Essay Writing Test, 50% of the students could write without spelling mistakes but in the 2nd Essay Writing Test 65% of the

students could use the correct spelling. And, in the 3rd Essay Writing Test, 80% of the students could write with the correct spelling.

In the use of tenses, in the 1st Test, only 20% of the students could use the tenses correctly whereas in the 2nd Test, 50% of the students could use the correct tenses. Moreover, in the 3rd Test, 85% of the students could use the tenses correctly.

In dealing with idea expression, in the 1st Test, only 15% of the students could write clearly what they wanted to express but in the 2nd Test, 60% of the students could use appropriately what they wanted to express and in the 3rd Test, 85% of the students could write clearly and vividly what they wanted to say.

Figure 5. The graph of the students' writing quality percentage from the results of three tests

According to Figure 5, we can know that in the 1st Test, 70% of the students could use the appropriate conjunctions but in the 2nd Test, 80% of the students used the conjunctions appropriately and in the 3rd Test, 90% of the students could use the conjunctions correctly. In concerning with the use of article, in the 1st Test, only 20% of the students could use the articles correctly whereas in the 2nd Test, 65% of the students could use the correct articles and in the 3rd Test, 95% of the students used the articles correctly. According to Figure 5, it may be seen that in the 1st Test, 50% of the students used the correct prepositions but in the 2nd Test, 85% of the students could use the prepositions correctly and in the 3rd Test, 100% of the students could use prepositions correctly. In dealing with the use of frequency adverbs, in the 1st Test, 80% of the students could use frequency adverbs correctly and in the 2nd Test, 90% of the students used the correct frequency adverbs. Moreover, in the 3rd Test, 100% of the students used frequency adverbs correctly.

According to the results of three tests, it can be seen that by being trained well in writing the students' qualities become higher and higher. So, English teachers should use various techniques and methods for teaching writing skills to promote their students' writing skill.

Conclusion

This paper is "An Extensive Study of Methods and Techniques for Teaching Writing Skills to Intermediate Level Students". So, the 46-item questionnaires concerning with teaching writing skills were given to teachers of English specialization from Yadanabon University, Mandalay to investigate how they teach writing skills to the intermediate level students. Moreover, the progress of intermediate level students' writing skill has been observed by giving one model essay and three tests. So, by comparing the three results in **each** grammatical role, it can be seen that the students' writing abilities are **higher and higher** in

each role from 1st Test to 3rd Test. So, it has been noticed that the students' writing abilities become higher and higher by being trained well in writing. Thus, to improve students' writing skill teachers of English specialization should use various techniques and methods for teaching writing and should train their students for writing skill at least once a week. Moreover, they should encourage their students to write as they can (e.g. essay writing, letter writing, etc.) and also encourage them not to be reluctant to write and write too much. By means of these, at last the students can write clearly and vividly what they want to express and they will become skillful in writing. So, it is hoped that the methods and techniques presented in this paper will be of great help to teachers of English specialization for teaching writing skills to their intermediate level students.

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